

CRITICAL EVALUATION OF SOCIAL FACTORS AFFECTING ACADEMIC PROCRASTINATION OF PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS

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Abstract

It is important to identify academic procrastination behaviours disrupting the educational life of students. It is also important to determine the academic procrastination tendencies and underlying causes in teachers and pre-service teachers, who are an inseparable part of the education environment. Although there have been intense studies by modern psychologists and researchers on these procrastination behaviours and possible reasons, Steel (2007) reported that there were many unknowns related to the tendency to procrastinate despite the increased interest in this subject. This research paper mainly deals with social factors (family, health and peer learning) affecting academic procrastination of preservice B.Ed. teachers, batch (2018-2020), studying at University of Mumbai. To critically evaluate the social factors affecting the academic procrastination behaviour of preservice teachers, a group of 511 pre-service teachers studying in both aided and non-aided B.Ed. colleges of University of Mumbai were selected. The Procrastination Assessment Scale for students (PASS) developed by Linda J. Solomon & Esther D. Rothblum (1984) and adapted by Özer and Ferrari (2011) was used in the study. Another tool prepared and used in the research was 'Factors of Academic procrastination. It contained 45 items, 15 items with respect to social factors. This tool was used only after content validation by more than 12 Ph.D. experts in the educational field. In the analyses of the data, arithmetic means, standard deviation, t-test and ANOVA analysis were used. According to the results obtained, a significant difference was observed in the social Factors and Overall Factors for Academic Procrastination, a significant difference in the social factors of Academic

Procrastination according to the Monthly Income of respondents, and according to the Type of Institution of respondents. There is no significant difference between Male and Female respondents with regard to Social Factors of Academic Procrastination.

Keywords: Procrastination, academic procrastination, pre-service teachers, peer learning

Introduction:

Many factors affect human behaviours. These factors can be social, cultural, physical, psychological or economic factors. In the modern world there are constantly increasing technological developments and scientific advances and these cause changes in the behaviours and attitudes in the life path of individuals. Increasing technological developments present individuals with a greater number and more rapid sources of communication and thereby increase the pace of daily life.

Just as an acceleration in daily life can provide advantages in both private and working life, it may also be a reason for accumulated tasks and tasks that require completion, thereby placing the individual in a disadvantageous situation. Tasks with accumulated responsibilities in particular increase the tendency of the individual to procrastination and cause them to exhibit procrastination behaviour. Although there have been intense studies by modern psychologists and researchers on these procrastination behaviours and possible reasons, Steel (2007)¹ reported that there were many unknowns related to the tendency to procrastinate despite the increased interest in this subject.

Studies on Academic Procrastination

The procrastination tendency was defined by Grecco (1984)² as the potential of a person to delay completion of an important task or job without showing a valid reason, and as a result of a procrastination tendency, the majority showed insufficient performance (Ferrari, O'Callaghan, & Newbegin, 2005; Solomon & Rothblum, 1984)³. Moreover, procrastination behaviour, which was identified as extremely widespread in adults, was determined to lead to stress and other diseases (Dewitte & Schouwenburg, 2002;

¹ Steel, P (2007), The nature of procrastination: A meta-analytic and theoretical review of quintessential self- regulatory failure. *Psychological Bulletin*, 133(1), 65–94.

² Grecco, Patrick Ronald, (1984). A cognitive-behavioral assessment of problematic academic procrastination: development of a procrastination self- statement inventory. Fresno. ProQuest Dissertations Publishing, 8508678.

³ Solomon, Laura J. & Rothblum, Esther D, (1984). Academic procrastination: Frequency and cognitive-behavioral correlates. *Journal of Counseling Psychology*

Fritzsche, Young, & Hickson, 2003; Tice & Baumeister, 2018)⁴. Hammer and Ferrari (2002) reported that 20% of adults displayed chronic procrastination behaviour in daily tasks and responsibilities, while other researchers determined that 70%-95% of high school students had a tendency for academic procrastination (Ellis & Knaus, 1977; Steel, 2007)⁵.

Although academic procrastination is examined in literature under the heading of general procrastination, Senecal, Koestner and Vallerand (1995)⁶ defined this as individuals not starting these tasks until they experience a high level of stress associated with not having fulfilled the necessary academic tasks at the right time. According to Scher and Osterman (2002)⁷, academic procrastination is a barrier to academic success, a significant source of stress for the student and a factor reducing the amount and quality of what is learned. In addition, when attention is drawn to the intensity of academic procrastination in university environments, it has been concluded that there is a correlation between the level of academic procrastination and low levels of self-organisation, academic self-sufficiency and self-confidence, and high levels of anxiety, stress and illness. (Ferrari et al., 2005; Howell, Watson, Powell, & Buro, 2006; Schraw, Wadkins, & Olafson, 2007; Tice & Baumeister, 2018; Wolters, 2003)⁸.

Academic procrastination and pre-service teachers

Just as it is important to identify academic procrastination behaviours disrupting the educational life of students, it is also important to determine the academic procrastination tendencies and underlying factors in teachers and pre-service teachers, who are an inseparable part of the education environment. Teachers spend the greater part of their day with the adults of the future and as a significant part of educational life have a role in educating them to be useful members of society. Furthermore, as examples to the students, the attitudes, behaviour and habits displayed by teachers play a major role in shaping the behaviours of students.

⁴ Dewitte, S., & Schouwenburg, H. C. (2002), Procrastination, temptations, and incentives: The struggle between the present and the future in procrastinators and the punctual. *European Journal of Personality*

⁵ Corey A. Hammer & Joseph R. Ferrari, (2002), Differential incidence of procrastination between blue and white-collar workers, *Current Psychology* volume 21, pages 333–338

⁶ Caroline Senécal, Richard Koestner & Robert J. Vallerand, (1995) Self-Regulation and Academic Procrastination, *The Journal of Social Psychology*, 135:5, 607-619

⁷ Steven J. Scher & Nicole M. Osterman, Procrastination, (2002) Conscientiousness, anxiety, and goals: Exploring the measurement and correlates of procrastination among school-aged children

⁸ Joseph R. Ferrari et al, (2005), Prevalence of Procrastination in the United States, United Kingdom, and Australia: Arousal and Avoidance Delays among Adults, No. 1, 1 -6.

Balkis (2006) emphasised that teachers should be equipped with professional skills such as timely and effective planning, self-organisation and non-procrastination of academic duties. Therefore, to train more successful teachers, it is important to firstly determine the factors of academic procrastination tendencies of pre-service teachers who will become the teachers of the future and to investigate the reasons underlying these tendencies.

The aim of this study was to examine and critically evaluate social factors affecting academic procrastination behaviours of pre-service B.Ed. teachers (batch 2018-20) in aided and non-aided colleges of Mumbai University.

The present study

The present study had two objectives. The first objective was to critically evaluate the social factors (family, health & peer learning) affecting the academic procrastination of pre-service teachers, batch (2018-2020), in two years B.Ed. programme of Mumbai University. The second objective was to study the social factors of academic procrastination according to gender of respondents. A sample size of 511 pre-service B.Ed. teachers of batch (2018-2020) was considered for the research, which included 12 B. Ed. Colleges, both aided and non-aided of Mumbai University. Two tools were used for data collection, one standardized tool (PASS) of (Solomon & Rothblum, 1984), later adapted by Özer and Ferrari (2011), and, another new tool was constructed and validated by more than 12 Ph.D. experts based on factors affecting Academic Procrastination. Both synchronous and asynchronous mode was adopted for collection of data. Google form containing questionnaires was prepared and the link mailed to the students and shared in the online google meet.

Summary table of descriptive statistics of **Social Factors and it's three components** are as follows.

Table 1

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS					
VARIABLE	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Health	511	20.00	100.00	46.18	16.98
Family	511	20.00	92.00	49.33	13.83
Peer Learning	511	20.00	88.00	46.63	14.62
Social factors	511	24.00	78.67	47.38	11.47

Presentation of Table and Interpretation

HYPOTHESIS I

Null Hypothesis H_{01C}: There is no significant difference between the Social Factors and Overall factors of Academic Procrastination.

Alternate Hypothesis H_{11C}: There is a significant difference between the Social Factors and Overall factors of Academic Procrastination.

Table 1.1: To test the above Null Hypothesis Paired t-test is applied, the p-value is calculated and is shown in the below table:

Table 1.1

PAIRED SAMPLES TEST						
		Paired Differences		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation			
Pair 1	Overall Factors for Academic Procrastination – Social factors	-1.83	6.44	-6.45	510	0.00

Interpretation: The p-value for the above pair is 0.000. This is less than 0.05 and hence significant at 5% level of significance. Hence, the Paired t-test is rejected for these pairs. Hence Null Hypothesis is rejected and Alternate hypothesis is accepted.

Conclusion: There is a significant difference in the Social Factors affecting the Academic Procrastination and Overall Factors for Academic Procrastination of respondents.

Finding is that the Social Factors affecting Academic Procrastination is significantly different from the Overall Factors for Academic Procrastination. The Overall Factors of Academic Procrastination is lesser as compared to the Social Factors affecting it. This can also be seen in the below table:

Table:1.2

PAIRED SAMPLES STATISTICS					
		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	Overall Factors for Academic Procrastination	45.54	511	11.38	0.50
	Social factors	47.38	511	11.47	0.50

The above table indicates that the mean score for the Overall Factors of Academic Procrastination is lesser at 54.45 percent, while the mean score for social factors is higher at 47.38 per cent.

HYPOTHESIS II

Null Hypothesis H_{02C}: There is no significant difference between Male and Female respondents with regard to Social Factors of Academic Procrastination.

Alternate Hypothesis H_{12C}: There is a significant difference between Male and Female respondents with regard to Social Factors of Academic Procrastination.

Table: 2 To test the above Null Hypothesis ANOVA is obtained and F-test is applied.

Table:2

ANOVA					
Social Factors					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p-value
Between Groups	193.63	1	193.63	1.47	0.22
Within Groups	66961.93	509	131.55		
Total	67155.56	510			

Interpretation: The above results indicate that calculated p-value is 0.22. It is more than 0.05 and hence not significant at 5% level of significance. Therefore F-test is accepted. Hence Null hypothesis is accepted and Alternate hypothesis is rejected.

Conclusion: There is no significant difference between Male and Female respondents with regard to Social Factors of Academic Procrastination.

Findings: It is that the difference in the Mean Score for Social Factors of Academic Procrastination is highly insignificant across the Gender of respondents. It is similar for both male and female respondents. This can be observed in the following table:

Table:2.1

Report			
Social factors			
Gender	Mean	N	Std. Deviation
Male	49.80	31	10.63
Female	47.22	480	11.51
Total	47.38	511	11.47

The above table indicates that the mean score for Social Factors of Academic Procrastination is highest at 49.80 percent for Male respondents, while it is lowest at 47.22 percent for Female respondents. This verifies our findings.

Discussion: The finding that there is a significant difference between the Social Factors and Overall factors of Academic Procrastination of respondents. This suggests that the variable social factor having subfactors as family, health and peer learning, have significant effect on academic procrastination of pre-service B.Ed. teachers of Mumbai University. Out of the three subfactors of social factor, **family**, is statistically (Mean Rank based on Friedman's Test) found to have the most effect on academic procrastination. Both health and peer learning have same mean rank value but less than that of family. This suggests that family plays an important role in affecting the academic procrastination of pre-service teachers, so responsibilities towards family, family related problems of preservice teachers are impacting or influencing them to delay their academic tasks and hence procrastinate. The finding that there is no significant difference between Male and Female respondents with regard to Social Factors of Academic Procrastination implies that social factors are influencing academic procrastination but irrespective of difference in gender. Both male and female pre-service teachers are equally influenced by social factors and gender has no role to play in that.

Conclusion:

From the results of the research and discussion, it can be concluded that the social factors are affecting academic procrastination of pre-service teachers and hence there is need to cater to all the related subgroups of social factors. Efforts are to be made both by the respondents and the stakeholders towards mitigating and preventing the occurrence of this common phenomenon among the pre-service teachers by adopting such measures which will be beneficial for the pre-service teachers and help them in bringing adjustment between academic tasks and social factors influencing their academic procrastination. Quality academic tasks require time, so proper time to be provided and alternate provisions to be given to respondents to submit their assignments and internal examinations. The difference in the mean score for social factors of academic procrastination is highly insignificant across the gender of respondents. It is similar for all respondents irrespective of their gender.

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